

Kinetics of adsorption of DNA at solid-liquid interfaces

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We have investigated the mechanistic aspect of DNA adsorption at different hydrophobic and hydrophilic solid-liquid interfaces as a function of bulk DNA concentration, pH, ionic strength, temperature. In all cases of DNA adsorption at solid-liquid interfaces, initial rate of adsorption is controlled by diffusion process and the steady value of extent of adsorption (T_2^s) is attained after nearly six hours. The rates of adsorption in all cases fit the first order rate equation with two kinetic constants k_1 and k_2 . Using the Arrhenius equation, the activation energies E_1^* and E_2^* for DNA adsorption have been evaluated. The corresponding values of enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger), entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger), and free energy of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) have been evaluated using Eyring's equation of absolute reaction rate. It has been found that $T_{av} \Delta S^\ddagger > \Delta H^\ddagger$ for both the kinetic steps, so adsorption of DNA at charcoal-water and silica-water interface is solely entropy-controlled. But in case of BaSO_4 -water interface, adsorption of DNA is enthalpy-controlled. Free energy of activation, ΔG_1^\ddagger and ΔG_2^\ddagger vary within 65 to 75 and 70 to 80 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively, and these values are comparable with adsorption of different proteins at solid-liquid interfaces.

Physicochemical investigations of different biopolymers at solid-liquid and liquid-liquid interfaces have attracted considerable interest in last few decades¹⁻⁸. Protein adsorption at solid-liquid, liquid-liquid and air-liquid interfaces is extremely important in the field of medical devices, pharmacy, biotechnology and cell culture, biochips, food technology etc. So a large number of publications regarding the aspects of protein adsorption are now available in literature. Protein adsorption has been extensively reviewed by Andrade⁹. Chattoraj *et al.*^{8,10-14} have extensively studied the equilibrium and kinetic aspects of protein adsorption at solid-liquid and liquid-liquid interfaces in different physicochemical conditions. In contrast, adsorption of the other biopolymers, DNA which is the most important polyelectrolyte controlling genetic aspects of living systems has not been studied in detail. But in recent years, the interest has grown up to know the physicochemical behavior of this natural polyelectrolyte at the interface for better understanding of the role of DNA in different physiological processes as well as to develop gene based therapy^{15,16}. DNA adsorption is also important to develop DNA-based biosensors which require efficient immobilization of DNA probes on the sensor surface¹⁷⁻²⁰. Genosensor, a DNA-based biosensor is a useful means for studying DNA-protein, DNA-ligand interactions²¹⁻²³. Recent studies reveal that *in vivo* gene transfer may be possible through the entrapment of negatively charged DNA by positively charged liposomes of cationic lipids^{24,25}. Development of cancer drug is one of the high prospect possible applications of this method. The method

of delivery of DNA into different types of human tissues using a 'genegun' has been developed²⁶⁻²⁹.

Several techniques, like microelectrophoresis³⁰, electron microscopy³¹, differential capacity measurement³², radio tracer³³ have been used for studying adsorption of DNA at different interfaces. Chattoraj *et al.*³⁴ have already investigated the adsorption of DNA at an alumina-water interface. The pH effect on adsorption of DNA on glass surface has been studied by Chari and Mookerjee³⁵. Recently, Gani *et al.*³⁶ have studied the equilibrium of adsorption of DNA from aqueous solution on different hydrophobic and hydrophilic solid surfaces as a function of pH, ionic strength, temperature and denaturants. But mechanistic aspects of adsorption of DNA on solid surface remain unexplored because kinetic study of this adsorption is rare in current available literature. Very recently Yang *et al.*³⁷ have studied the adsorption kinetics of thiol-modified double stranded DNA on gold surface.

In the present communication, the adsorption kinetics of DNA on charcoal, powdered barium sulfate and powdered silica have been investigated in different physicochemical conditions. An attempt has been made to compare the kinetic aspects of adsorption in different cases from the values of rate constants for different steps of adsorption. Diffusion coefficients for adsorption process has been computed. The activation parameters of different kinetics steps have also been evaluated for DNA adsorption at solid-liquid interfaces.

Fig. 1. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs time t for the adsorption of different concentration of DNA (moles nucleotide/lit) at the charcoal-water interface at pH = 6.0, $\mu = 0.05$: (A) $C_2^1 = 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$, $T = 293$ K, (B) $C_2^1 = 3 \times 10^{-4}$, $T = 293$ K, (C) $C_2^1 = 6 \times 10^{-4}$, $T = 298$ K.

Results and Discussion

In Figs. 1–4, moles of nucleotide (Γ_2^1) adsorbed per square meter of surface of powdered charcoal have been plotted against elapse time t under different physicochemical conditions. Rate of adsorption in each case is observed to be initially rapid in nature. Initial rate of adsorption [i.e. slope $(d\Gamma_2^1/dt)_{t \rightarrow 0}$] increases in all cases with increase of the concentration of DNA in bulk solution. This indicates that rate of adsorption is initially controlled by diffusion process. With increase of t further, Γ_2^1 increases slowly and it reaches a steady nearly constant value when t is high. This steady value is attained when t is nearly six hours time. In the case of small surfactants adsorbed at the charcoal surface, such steady value of t is attained at elapsed time nearly 30 min, whereas for proteins, t is nearly one hour elapsed time when steady value of Γ_2^1 is attained. Steady value of Γ_2^1 is thus strongly dependent on the size of the adsorbate molecules.

For the same value of DNA concentration in the bulk,

Fig. 2. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs time t for the adsorption of DNA at the charcoal-water interface at pH = 6.0, $\mu = 0.05$, $C_2^1 = 3 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit) : (A) 293, (B) 303, (C) 318 K.

Γ_2^1 - t plot for powdered charcoal is significantly dependent on temperatures (Fig. 2). The initial slope of Γ_2^1 - t plot as well as steady value Γ_2^e usually increase with increase of temperature. This may indicate that the adsorption process is endothermic and controlled significantly by hydrophobic interaction.

In Fig. 3, Γ_2^1 - t plot for adsorption of DNA on charcoal have been compared at pHs 8.0, 6.0 and 4.0. Values of tem-

Fig. 3. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs time t for the adsorption of DNA at the charcoal-water interface at $\mu = 0.05$, $T = 303$ K, $C_2^1 = 3 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit) : (A) pH 8.0, (B) pH 4.0, (C) pH 6.0.

perature, ionic strength and total bulk DNA concentration remained same in all these cases. The Γ_2^1 - t curve at pH 4.0 is different from those at pHs 6.0 and 8.0 although initial slope at the three pH values are very close to each other. In pH 4.0, the extent of adsorption of DNA is higher than that at pH 6.0 or 8.0.

In Fig. 4, Γ_2^1 - t curves for DNA adsorption on charcoal have been compared in the presence of different neutral salts which affect hydration of DNA to different extents. Initial

Fig. 4. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs time t for the adsorption of DNA at the charcoal-water interface in presence of different electrolytes at pH = 6.0, $\mu = 0.2$, $C_2^1 = 3 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit) : (A) NaCl, (B) LiCl, (C) KCl, (D) CaCl₂ + NaCl.

slope in all parts are close to each other. But Γ_2^e is observed to depend on the nature of the salts.

Any first order kinetics can be represented by the rate equation,

$$d\Gamma_2^1/dt = k [\Gamma_2^e - \Gamma_2^1] \quad (1)$$

Integration of eqn. (1) leads to the relation,

$$-\ln [\Gamma_2^e - \Gamma_2^1] = k t + \ln \lambda \quad (2)$$

where Γ_2^1 is the extent of adsorption at any time t , and Γ_2^e is the extent of adsorption when an equilibrium state of adsorption is reached, k stands for first order rate constant and λ is a constant of integration. Previously rate constants of protein adsorption on silica and other surfaces^{12,13} have been

Fig. 5. Plots of $-\ln [\Gamma_2^e - \Gamma_2^1]$ vs time t for the adsorption of DNA at the charcoal-water interface at $\text{pH} = 6.0, \mu = 0.5$: (A) $C_2^1 = 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit), $T = 293$ K, (B) $C_2^1 = 3.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit), $T = 293$ K, (C) $C_2^1 = 6.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit), $T = 298$ K.

calculated using eqn. (2). In Fig. 5, the plot of $\ln [\Gamma_2^e - \Gamma_2^1]$ vs t gives two straight lines with two different slopes. This indicates that DNA molecules are attached to the solid surface directly and rate of this process follows first order kinetics of eqn. (2) and the rate constant of this process may be identified with k_1 . At higher values of t , the surface becomes crowded with biopolymers molecules so that free space in the surface becomes limited. The adsorbed molecules at the interface alters orientation slowly due to polymer-polymer interaction which allows accommodation of more molecules at the interface. The rate of the orientation process may be identified with rate constant k_2 . Similar process has already been observed for the adsorption of surfactants and proteins at interfaces^{12,13,41}.

Alternatively, in all systems undergoing first order kinetic processes, the rate constants k_1 and k_2 have been evaluated following the rate equation,

$$\Gamma_2^1 = \Gamma_2^e - A_1 e^{-k_1 t} - A_2 e^{-k_2 t} \quad (3)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are rate constants of two different steps and A_1 and A_2 their pre-exponential amplitude terms. At $t = 0$, $\Gamma_2^1 = 0$, so that eqn. (3) can be written as

$$A_1 + A_2 = \Gamma_2^e \quad (4)$$

Values of the exponential terms of eqn. (3) initially falls sharply with increase of time but at a higher interval of time their values slowly but asymptotically approaches zero when Γ_2^1 approaches the value of Γ_2^e . The rate constants for different systems evaluated by computer analysis are presented in Tables 1–3. These are close to the values of k_1 and k_2 obtained from the slope of the plot, $-\ln [\Gamma_2^e - \Gamma_2^1]$ vs t .

From Table 1 one notes with interest that k_1 and k_2 regularly increase with increase of C_2 . This is expected since rate of reaction between DNA and surface of carbon will increase with increase of C_2 . Rate constants k_1 and k_2 of this reaction also increase with increase of temperature so that from the Arrhenius plot of $\ln k_1$ and $\ln k_2$ vs $1/T$, respectively, (Fig. 6) values of energies of activation E_1^* and

Fig. 6. Plots of $-\ln k_1$ (A,B) or $-\ln k_2$ (C,D) vs $1/T$ for the adsorption of DNA at the charcoal-water interface at $\text{pH} = 6.0, \mu = 0.05$: (A,C) $C_2^1 = 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit), (B,D) $C_2^1 = 3.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (mole nucleotide/lit).

E_2^* for the first (anchorage) and second (orientation change) processes have been calculated. These values for adsorption of DNA on charcoal surfaces at different bulk concentrations of DNA are presented in Table 4. Although $k_1 \gg k_2$, for each system, values of E_1^* and E_2^* are not far from each other. E_1^* values for protein adsorption on silica surface are higher than that for DNA adsorption on charcoal or silica¹³. But values of E_2^* are comparable in adsorption of both biopolymers protein and DNA at different solid-liquid

Table 1. Kinetic parameters of adsorption of DNA at charcoal-water interface at different physicochemical conditions

Conc. of DNA (moles nucleotide/ lit) $C_2^1 \times 10^4$	pH	Ionic strength	Temp. K	k_1 h^{-1}	k_2 h^{-1}	RMSD*
1.5	6	0.05	293	1.20	0.090	0.02
1.5	6	0.05	303	1.70	0.141	0.02
1.5	6	0.05	318	2.80	0.170	0.03
3.0	6	0.05	293	5.50	0.170	0.02
3.0	6	0.05	303	6.00	0.190	0.02
3.0	6	0.05	318	7.10	0.210	0.02
6.0	6	0.05	298	8.00	0.120	0.02
6.0	6	0.05	318	10.0	0.140	0.03
3.0	6	0.15	300	2.20	0.080	0.02
3.0	6	0.25	300	1.50	0.060	0.02
1.5	4	0.05	293	1.60	0.350	0.01
1.5	4	0.05	304	2.29	0.390	0.03
1.5	4	0.05	318	3.10	0.430	0.04
3.0	4	0.05	293	2.60	0.270	0.04
3.0	4	0.05	303	3.00	0.300	0.05
3.0	4	0.05	311	3.40	0.330	0.04
6.0	4	0.05	303	6.50	0.130	0.05
1.5	8	0.05	294	4.80	0.170	0.02
1.5	8	0.05	303	6.20	0.190	0.02
1.5	8	0.05	311	8.00	0.220	0.02
3.0	8	0.05	294	7.50	0.170	0.02
3.0	8	0.05	303	8.60	0.180	0.02
3.0	8	0.05	308	9.00	0.210	0.02
6.0	8	0.05	303	10.6	0.160	0.03

*Root mean square deviations.

interfaces. From Table 1, one also notes that for charcoal surface, values of k_1 at pH 8.0 is higher in magnitude than that at pH 6.0, but values of k_1 at pHs 6.0 and 4.0 are closer to each other. At pH 8.0, DNA is extensively alkali-denatured so that rate of adsorption of unfolded DNA becomes higher than that of native DNA, double helix structure assumed to exist at pH 6.0. DNA is extensively acid-denatured much below pH 4.0 so that values of k_1 at pHs 6.0 and 4.0 are not widely different from each other.

In Table 2, values of k_1 and k_2 have been evaluated for adsorption of Na-salt of DNA at charcoal surface in presence of 0.2 ionic strength of LiCl, NaCl and KCl and $CaCl_2 + NaCl$ respectively at three different temperatures. Values of k_1 and k_2 in all these cases do not widely vary from each other. The hydration of DNA in presence of these salts are known to vary widely⁴² but the rate constant values is not sensitive to change in biopolymers hydration. The values of E_1^* and E_2^* respectively are also of same order of magni-

tude (Table 4).

Table 2. Adsorption kinetic parameters of DNA at charcoal-water interface in presence of different electrolytes

pH = 6.0, ionic strength = 0.2 M

Salt	Conc. of DNA (moles nucleotide/ lit) $C_2^1 \times 10^4$	Temp. K	k_1 h^{-1}	k_2 h^{-1}	RMSD*
LiCl	3.0	293	3.00	0.150	0.03
LiCl	3.0	305	4.00	0.170	0.04
NaCl	3.0	289	2.01	0.060	0.04
NaCl	3.0	298	2.95	0.080	0.04
NaCl	3.0	308	4.02	0.100	0.04
KCl	3.0	293	5.40	0.180	0.03
KCl	3.0	298	6.15	0.190	0.03
KCl	3.0	303	6.80	0.220	0.04
$CaCl_2 + NaCl$	3.0	303	4.00	0.160	0.03

* Root mean square deviations.

In Table 3, values of k_1 and k_2 have been presented for the surface barium sulfate and silica. Figs. 7 and 8 have revealed the Γ_2^1 variation with time for adsorption of DNA on barium sulfate at pH 4.0 and on silica at pH 8.0, respec-

Table 3. Kinetic parameters of adsorption of DNA at different solid-water interfaces

Surface	pH	Ionic strength	Temp. K	Conc. of DNA (moles nucleotide/ lit) $C_2^1 \times 10^4$	k_1 h^{-1}	k_2 h^{-1}	RMSD*
BaSO ₄	4.0	0.05	303	1.5	3.20	0.850	0.06
	4.0	0.05	288	3.0	2.30	0.150	0.11
	4.0	0.05	295	3.0	4.48	0.290	0.14
	4.0	0.05	303	3.0	7.00	0.450	0.12
	4.0	0.15	303	3.0	2.00	0.010	0.16
Silica	8.0	0.05	295	3.0	0.80	0.140	0.13
	8.0	0.05	301	3.0	0.88	0.160	0.10
	8.0	0.05	307	3.0	1.00	0.190	0.01
	8.0	0.05	307	6.0	1.41	0.080	0.22

*Root mean square deviations.

tively. In other experimental pH, the adsorption of DNA on these two surfaces is too low to determine the kinetics. For barium sulfate surface, the k_1 and k_2 values are not widely different from that obtained from charcoal surface at the same experimental condition. k_1 values of adsorption of DNA on silica are much lower than the k_1 values obtained from the adsorption of DNA on charcoal surface in similar condition. The values of E_1^* and E_2^* for barium sulfate are significantly higher than charcoal surface. k_1 values of adsorption of DNA on solid surfaces, are almost comparable with

that obtained from protein adsorption on silica surface, investigated by Sarkar and Chattoraj previously. Of course the k_2 values here are much lower than the k_2 values of the same study¹³. Activation energy (E_1^*) which is needed for transfer of 1 mole DNA from bulk to surface is also lower than 1 mole of protein at silica surface from bulk. Activation energy (E_2^*) needed for the orientation of the adsorbed molecules at the surface are almost of same order for these two biopolymers, i.e. DNA and protein¹³. E_2^* of small molecules like surfactant adsorption on silica⁴¹ and charcoal⁴² surfaces is larger in most cases than DNA adsorption.

In Fig. 9, $\ln k_1/T$ and $\ln k_2/T$ for adsorption at charcoal

Fig. 7. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs time t for the adsorption of DNA at the barium sulfate-water interface at pH = 4.0, $T = 303$ K : (A) $C_2^1 = 1.5 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit), $\mu = 0.05$, (B) $C_2^1 = 3 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit), $\mu = 0.15$, (C) $C_2^1 = 3 \times 10^{-4}$ (mole nucleotide/lit), $\mu = 0.05$.

surface have been plotted against $1/T$. Plots in such cases are found to be linear as expected from Eyring equation,

$$\ln(k/T) = (\ln k/h + \Delta S^\ddagger/R) - \Delta H^\ddagger/RT \quad (5)$$

where h and k stand for Plank and Boltzman constants, respectively and ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger represent enthalpy and entropy of activation, respectively. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger for different systems are presented in Table 4. It has been noted that ΔH_1^\ddagger and ΔH_2^\ddagger both decrease with increase of bulk DNA concentration for the adsorption on charcoal surface. In presence of 0.2 M salts like LiCl, NaCl and KCl, the ΔH_1^\ddagger and ΔH_2^\ddagger values are higher than in absence of these salts. Since $T_{ave} \Delta S^\ddagger$ is higher than ΔH^\ddagger for both the kinetic steps, so adsorption of DNA at charcoal-water interface is solely entropy-controlled. Activation energy (E^*) for adsorption at barium sulfate-water is higher than adsorption on charcoal surface at pH 4.0. In contrast to charcoal and silica surface, the adsorption of DNA on barium sulfate is enthalpy-controlled. E^* of adsorption of DNA at silica-water interface at pH 8.0 is slightly higher than charcoal surface at the same pH. Sarkar and Chattoraj observed that anchorage of protein at silica-water interface is mostly enthalpy-controlled process whereas the reorientation step is mostly entropy-controlled at the activated step. Biswas and Chattoraj⁴¹ obtained entropy-controlled activation reaction for the adsorption of small molecules like cationic surfactant at silica-water interface. For adsorption of DNA at different solid-liquid interfaces, the values of ΔG_1^\ddagger vary within 65–75 kJ mol⁻¹ whereas ΔG_2^\ddagger vary within 70–80 kJ mol⁻¹. It was observed previously that in case of protein adsorption at silica-water interface, the ΔG_1^\ddagger and ΔG_2^\ddagger values are close to each other in magnitude¹³. The ΔG_1^\ddagger and ΔG_2^\ddagger values for

Table 4. Activation energy parameters for dynamic adsorption of DNA at different solid-water interfaces

Conc. of DNA (moles nucleotide/lit)		Surface	pH	Ionic strength	E^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)		ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)		$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)		ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)		$-T_{ave} \Delta S^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	
$C_2^1 \times 10^4$					E_1^*	E_2^*	ΔH_1^\ddagger	ΔH_2^\ddagger	ΔS_1^\ddagger	ΔS_2^\ddagger	ΔG_1^\ddagger	ΔG_2^\ddagger	$T_{ave} \Delta S_1^\ddagger$	$T_{ave} \Delta S_2^\ddagger$
1.5			6.0	0.05	24.1	16.5	23.4	16.2	0.163	0.208	73.1	79.8	49.6	63.3
3.0			6.0	0.05	7.51	6.66	5.30	3.90	0.212	0.246	70.0	78.8	64.5	74.9
6.0			6.0	0.05	8.70	6.07	6.33	0.86	0.206	0.250	69.8	77.8	63.4	77.0
3.0		Charcoal	6.0	0.2LiCl	17.8	17.0	14.8	4.75	0.184	0.244	70.1	77.7	55.0	72.9
3.0	6.0		0.2NaCl	26.9	19.8	23.7	16.6	0.156	0.210	70.3	79.3	46.5	62.6	
3.0	6.0		0.2KCl	17.0	14.8	15.1	12.6	0.179	0.215	68.4	76.9	53.3	64.0	
1.5			4.0	0.05	21.1	6.56	18.5	4.03	0.177	0.239	72.9	77.3	53.9	72.8
3.0			4.0	0.05	11.1	7.68	7.79	5.57	0.210	0.236	71.3	77.1	63.4	71.3
1.5			8.0	0.05	24.5	11.5	20.7	9.09	0.161	0.228	69.6	78.3	48.7	69.0
3.0			8.0	0.05	11.9	10.9	8.23	7.86	0.200	0.198	68.6	67.8	60.5	59.9
3.0		BaSO ₄	4.0	0.05	54.0	53.7	52.0	51.3	0.056	0.082	68.7	75.6	16.5	24.2
3.0		Silica	8.0	0.05	14.2	19.2	12.1	17.2	0.205	0.202	74.0	78.3	61.7	60.8

Fig. 8. Plots of Γ_2^1 vs time t for the adsorption of DNA at the silica-water interface at pH = 8.0, $\mu = 0.05$, $T = 307$ K : (A) $C_2^1 = 3.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit), (B) $C_2^1 = 6.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit).

adsorption of DNA and protein at solid-liquid interface are comparable.

Diffusion coefficients (D_s) for adsorption process have been evaluated using Bull's equation for such stirred system⁴³,

$$(d\Gamma_2^1/dt)_{t \rightarrow 0} = D_s C_2^1 / \delta \times 10^3 \quad (6)$$

where δ is the thickness of the stagnant layer adhered to the solid surface, and its value was taken to be of the order of 10^{-4} m⁴⁴. The values of D_s , obtained for the adsorption of DNA are in the order of 10^{-18} m² s⁻¹ whereas Sarkar and Chattoraj¹³ obtained the values of D_s in the order of 10^{-13} m² s⁻¹ for protein adsorption on silica. We note from Table 5 that the values of D_s also decrease with increase of bulk DNA concentration. Biswas and Chattoraj⁴¹ obtained similar trends for adsorption of cationic surfactants solid-liquid interface.

In the kinetics of adsorption at solid-liquid interface, both water and biopolymers, here DNA from the bulk competes to occupy surface active spots present at the surface of the silica. It has been already shown that Γ_2^1 is equal to $(\Delta n_2 - \Delta n_1 C_2)/55.5$, which appears to remain valid for equilibrium as well as non-equilibrium states so that we may write,

$$d\Gamma_2^1/dt = d(\Delta n_2)/dt - C_2^1 d(\Delta n_1)/55.5 dt \quad (7)$$

In Fig. 8, we note that for DNA adsorption at silica-water interface, Γ_2^1 is negative below t less than 1 h because Δn_2

Fig. 9. Plots of $-\ln k_1/T$ (A,B,C) or $-\ln k_2/T$ (D,E) vs $1/T$ for the adsorption of DNA at charcoal-water interface at $\mu = 0.05$, $C_2^1 = 3.0 \times 10^{-4}$ (moles nucleotide/lit) : (A) pH 6.0, (B,D) pH 4.0, (C,E) pH 8.0.

is less than $\Delta n_1 C_2/55.5$.

Experimental

Calf thymus DNA (lot no. 67F-9725; Sigma), chromatographic grade silica powder (mesh size 60–120; Qualigen's Fine chemicals) crystalline granular charcoal (C 2889, mesh 8–20; Sigma) and powdered barium sulfate (G.R., Loba Chemical) were used. Before use, the inorganic solid sur-

Table 5. Diffusion coefficient (D_s) of adsorption of DNA at different solid-water interface

Surface	pH	Temp. K	$C_2^1 \times 10^4$ (moles nucleotide/lit)	Ionic strength	Initial slope		
					$(d\Gamma_2^1/dt)_{t \rightarrow 0} \times 10^8$ (moles nucleotide/m ² h)	$D_s \times 10^{14}$ (m ² /h)	$D_s \times 10^{18}$ m ² /s
Charcoal	6.0	303	1.5	0.05	3.78	2.52	7.00
Charcoal	6.0	303	3.0	0.05	4.54	1.51	4.20
Charcoal	6.0	298	6.0	0.05	7.57	1.26	3.50
Charcoal	4.0	303	3.0	0.05	2.65	0.883	2.45
Charcoal	8.0	303	3.0	0.05	1.89	0.630	1.75
BaSO ₄	4.0	303	3.0	0.05	4.54	1.51	4.20

faces were repeatedly washed with distilled water and dried nearly at 300° for several hours. All dried surfaces were kept in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂. Na₂HPO₄, NaH₂PO₄, NaOAc all other common electrolytes and acids were of A.R. grade. Stock 20 mg% (i.e. 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ moles nucleotide/lit) of DNA solutions were prepared using phosphate buffer for pH 6.0 and 8.0 and acetate buffer for pH 4.0 and in each case ionic strength was maintained at 0.05 M. These stock solutions were preserved in a refrigerator. For a particular set of experiment, the solution of required concentration was prepared by proper dilution of the stock solution. Double-distilled water was used for the preparation of all kinds of solutions. The average surface area of powdered barium sulfate and silica were measured³⁸ by the method of palmitic acid adsorption from dry benzene solution at 28°. The average surface area thus determined for silica and barium sulfate were found to be 100 ± 1 and 62.2 ± 0.2 m²/g, respectively. The surface area of charcoal was determined by the method of acetic acid adsorption from aqueous medium; it was 64 m²/g. For a comparison of the optical densities of a solution of DNA in 0.1 M NaCl at 260 and 230 nm as well as from a negative Folin reagent test, the absence of protein in the sample was confirmed.

For the study of adsorption kinetics, a definite amount of dried particles was taken into each standard joint - stoppered flask of 100 ml capacity. Then definite volume (20 ml) of DNA solution of known concentration was added into each flask. The time of addition was recorded in each case. The flasks were shaken in a horizontal shaker. At different intervals of time, each flask was taken away from the shaker and a definite volume of aliquot was collected from the supernate solution. For charcoal and barium sulfate, centrifuge was done to settle down the suspended particles. Then the DNA concentration after adsorption was measured in each case spectrophotometrically at 260 nm.

The moles of nucleotide adsorbed per square meter of surface (Γ_2^1) was calculated using the expression,

$$\Gamma_2^1 = \frac{(C_2^1 - C_2) V^1}{1000} \quad (1)$$

where V^1 stands for the volume of DNA solution in milliliters per square meter of solid surface and is equal to V/WA , where V is the volume of DNA solution in milliliters to which W grams of solid powder was added. To determine the Γ_2^c (i.e. amount of DNA adsorbed at equilibrium), the flasks were shaken for 24 h and kept undisturbed for another 4 h. At the end of this period, the DNA concentration in the bulk solution was determined spectrophotometrically

at 260 nm. The standard deviation in the measurement of Γ_2^1 was 4–8 % based on three sets of a single experimental setup. The error has been graphically presented in Fig. 1.

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